

RRI2SCALE – Co-creation Workshop Questionnaire (M2.3)

Title: RRI2SCALE agenda-setting workshop

Description: This questionnaire aims to measure the performance and impact of the RRI2SCALE agenda-setting workshop that took place recently.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are < Insert Regional Authority Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of RRI2SCALE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: RRI2SCALE - Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (GA Number 872526).

Partner: Organisation name: < Insert Regional Authority Name >

Address: < Insert Regional Authority Address >

Phone: < Insert Regional Authority Phone >

E-mail: < Insert Regional Authority Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons: 1. Project Manager: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

2. Data Protection Officer: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 7 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to the project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email or on the phone with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by RRI2SCALE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as workshops and other materials.	

Please reply to the following questions.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	PE.0.3	Would you describe the discussion as a good opportunity for your region to advance towards collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility?						
2	E.O.1	Do you think policy-makers should often organise discussions like the one you just participated in to allow future policies to reflect people’s needs, preferences and concerns and be aligned with social values?						
3	GO.PE.1	Do you think policy-makers should often organise discussions like the one you just participated in to not only consult citizens on their preferences but also to co-create solutions with them?						
4	E.O.3	Do you think discussions like the one you just participated in can increase citizens’ trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems?						
5	SDG.8.1	Do you think policies developed through discussions like the one you just participated in can promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society?						
6	SDG.10.1	Do you think policies developed through discussions like the one you just participated in can promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region?						

Please reply to the following questions.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	PE.0.2	Was the topic discussed today interesting and/or important for you?						
2	PE.0.1	Did you feel that the moderator(s) seriously considered the participants' opinions, values,						

		and expectations to be incorporated into future agendas and/or policies?						
3	PE.PE.1	Did your participation in the discussion increase your interest in policies affecting growth, innovation and equality in your region?						
4	PE.PE.3	In the future, would you actively participate in similar discussions to co-design policies that affect growth, innovation and equality in your region?						
5	GO.PR.1	Do you think more people in your region would perceive discussions like the one you just participated in as meaningful and happily participate in the future?						
6	PE.PR.7	After all, do you believe you had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to participate in the conversation actively?						

What did you like the most about the discussion, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

You participated in this survey as a member of:

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify?

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

Do you participate in this survey as a member of a governmental body or a regional authority? If yes, then please reply to the following two questions. Otherwise, ignore them.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	SP.EP.2	Did your participation in the discussion contribute to perceiving the engagement of various stakeholders in the region's strategic planning as a measure to democratise decision-making?						
2	SP.EP.3	In the future, would you undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the strategic planning of your region?						

Do you participate in this survey as a member of academia or research? If yes, then please reply to the following two questions. Otherwise, ignore them.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	GO.PE.2	Should universities in your region organise similar discussions to co-create with citizens the purposes or design of their research activities?						
2	PE.PE.4	In the future, would you undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the research activities of your organisation?						

Thank you for your feedback!